

The Effect of Transfer Pricing Aggressiveness and Thin Capitalization on Tax Avoidance

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ABSTRACT: Tax avoidance is a company's effort to find loopholes in tax rules and regulations so that the amount of tax paid is lower. In practice, companies can use transfer pricing and thin capitalization options as an effort to reduce the tax burden. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of transfer pricing and thin capitalization on tax avoidance. Tax avoidance as the dependent variable, transfer pricing and thin capitalization as independent variables. The population used in this study are all consumer cyclicals companies listed on the IDX for the 2017-2019 period. The sample in this study were 32 companies from the total 123 consumer cyclicals companies. The sampling technique was selected by purposive sampling method. The data source used is secondary data. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis with the help of SPSS version 26. The results of this study indicate that thin capitalization has an effect on tax avoidance while transfer pricing has no effect on tax avoidance.

Keywords: tax avoidance, transfer pricing, thin capitalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many countries in the world rely on tax revenues as their main source of income, including Indonesia. To finance all the needs of government administration, Indonesia requires a large amount of funds. Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 17 of 2003 concerning State Finances in Article 11 paragraph 3, namely: sources of state income are obtained from tax revenues, non-tax state revenues, and grants. Based on data from the Ministry of Finance, tax revenue in 2019 was around 82.5% from APBN sources. The role of taxes is very vital when viewed from the proportion and nominal value in funding the APBN.

Table 1. Budget and Realization of Tax Revenue for 2016-2019 (Trillion Rupiah)

Year	Budget	Realization
2016	1,539.2	1,285.0
2017	1,472.7	1,343.5
2018	1,618.1	1,518.8
2019	1786.4	1,643.1

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics (data processed)

If seen from the table above, the tax revenue budget has increased from 2016-2019. On the other hand, the target for the realization of tax revenue from year to year does not reach the target set by the State Budget. This lack of state revenue from the taxation sector has pushed the government through the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT) to increase the amount of tax revenue in this very potential sector. However, the government's strategy in increasing tax revenue can be said to be successful if it can run in harmony with taxpayers. In the classification of taxpayers in Indonesia, there are two first, individual taxpayers and corporate taxpayers who are given supremacy in determining the size of the tax payable through an annual notification letter (SPT) that is submitted. This is as stated in the Indonesian taxation rules which apply a tax collection system with a self-assessment system. With the self-assessment system, individual and corporate taxpayers both have the opportunity to reduce the tax burden. Because in business activities the main goal is maximum profit. In an effort to achieve this goal, large and small companies both want to reduce company costs, including the tax burden (Sjahril et al., 2020).

From the explanation above, there is a tendency that companies minimize taxes payable by means of tax planning. Tax avoidance can be a reflection of the strategy of tax planning. Furthermore, tax avoidance can facilitate companies in various ways, the goal is that companies can minimize tax payments by taking advantage of loopholes in tax law regulations (loopholes). In line with this thought, according to Hidayat (2018), tax avoidance is considered a legitimate way to save on tax payments as long as it does not go out of the established tax rules. From the understandings of tax avoidance above, the authors conclude that tax avoidance activities in companies are aThis can be taken to escape excessive tax payments by not violating tax rules in order to reduce the nominal tax burden.

Tax avoidance schemes by utilizing debt treatment that can generate interest as a reduction in gross income can result in

not achieving a country's tax revenue target which can be seen by decreasing effective tax rates. If the ETR value of a company is indicated to be low, it will have an impact on more effective tax avoidance practices and vice versa the ETR value of a company that is indicated to be high indicates the possibility of the company doing tax avoidance is very small (Wulandari&Septiari, 2015). In practice, tax avoidance in companies can use transfer pricing options, aggressiveness and thin capitalization as a bridge to reduce the tax burden.

Liu et al (2017) define transfer pricing as setting prices for internal (intrafirm) transactions. It also refers to pricing for transactions between related companies that involve the transfer of property, services, intangible goods and capital flows between related parties. When affiliate companies set prices, this is often interpreted and perceived as mispricing (an indication that the market is inefficient), which is a subjective system of forcing prices to be inconsistent with conditions. Viewed from the managerial accounting point of view, transfer pricing in a company tries to cut the tax burden so that it gets a bigger profit by setting prices by organizational departments to other organizational departments that are in the same company (Rahmiati& Sandi, 2016).

In Indonesia, the definition of transfer price is regulated in the Regulation of the Director General of Taxes Number PER-22/PJ/2013. The regulation states that affiliate transactions are referred to as transactions between related parties. The price that has been determined at the time of the affiliate transaction is referred to as transfer pricing. Then, the minister of finance issued a regulation in the Regulation of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia Number 213/PMK.03/2016 which contains transfer pricing as an instrument in affiliated transactions. Determination of transfer prices in transfer pricing activities easily occurs if there is a special relationship between the two parties. Transfer pricing is a transaction between taxpayers who

establish a special relationship or also called a related party transaction to maximize profits (Refgia, 2017). According to the Director General of Taxes, SuryoUtomo, transfer pricing is a practice that is still justified, but the illogical determination of transfer prices makes the practice less precise (www.pajak.go.id).

In addition to transfer pricing, the company's strategy to avoid tax can also be carried out by using thin capitalization practices. The strategy of thin capitalization describes the formation of a company's capital structure with a debt percentage greater than capital (Khomsatun&Martani, 2015). Meanwhile, according to Afifah&Prastiwi (2019), thin capitalization is a company tactic in tax avoidance schemes by looking for loopholes in existing tax regulations by changing capital participation to related parties into loans that are included directly or with intermediaries. Thin capitalization scheme is one of the practices that underlie tax avoidance.

In tax regulations, it is justified that corporate financing with debt can generate interest expense as an element of deductible taxable income (Afifah&Prastiwi, 2019). Meanwhile, corporate financing with capital, which is oriented towards dividends is not included in the deduction of taxable income (non-deductible). This situation encourages the parent company to inject as much capital structure as possible in the form of debt into the capital structure of overseas subsidiaries. Meanwhile, in the Minister of Finance Regulation Number 169/PMK.010/2015 it is stated that in the practice of thin capitalization, the amount of debt and capital is not allowed to be more than 4:1. This shows that there are differences of interest in the practice of thin capitalization which for the company is a legally valid way to get maximum profit. Meanwhile, from the state side, the widespread practice of thin capitalization causes state revenues from the tax sector to be lost quite large (Setiawan&Agustina, 2018).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency Theory (Agency Theory)

According to Schroeder et al (2019), agency theory is considered as a conflict that occurs between shareholders who are also owners of the company and management (agents). This conflict stems from an unequal interest between the first party (shareholders) and the second party (agent). According to Adityamurti&Ghozali (2017) tax avoidance can cause a problem called the agency problem. The emergence of agency problems in the practice of tax avoidance is because there are differences in interests between the agent and the principal, from the side of the manager as the executor of the practice of tax avoidance, he wants to increase compensation, while the principal wants to have a high rate of return on the amount of resources that have been spent (investment) including efficiency. tax expense.

Thin Capitalization

Prastiwi&Ratnasari (2019) interpret thin capitalization as part of tax avoidance practices. Thin capitalization is a practice in which the parent company over-finances the subsidiary, by injecting funds in the form of debt rather than capital. In this case, the company takes advantage of the difference in tax treatment of debt that generates interest (in return for debt) on the other hand, capital related to the distribution of dividends (in return for capital) will be taxed. Swelling corporate debt is an indication that a company is doing tax avoidance, this is because interest costs arising from debt are one of the deduction elements in taxable income. On the other hand, dividends are not an element that can be deducted from taxable income (Puspita&Febrianti, 2018). Due to the different treatment characteristics between interest and dividends, it becomes an opportunity for tax avoidance practices (Olivia &Dwimulyani, 2019).

Transfer Pricing

According to the OECD in Panjulusman et al (2018), transfer pricing is defined as the determination of prices between group members in multinational companies on the basis of agreements between group members that have the potential to deviate from the fair market price. Transfer pricing is a price determination made by company management to reduce the tax burden, thereby affecting a country's tax revenues and dividends received by shareholders (Herianti&Chairina,

2019). However, transfer pricing is widely used by companies to facilitate tax avoidance practices (Nugraha&Kristanto, 2019). In their research, Amidu et al (2019) found the role of transfer pricing in international tax avoidance. The first, Transfer pricing is used as a resource allocator and practice of tax avoidance with a view to obtaining high divisional profits. The second is used to facilitate multinational companies to move their funds internationally. This is because multinational companies operate and have subsidiaries in many countries and there is one head office that coordinates global management. The third, as an evaluation of the performance of subsidiaries, maximizes profit receipts by minimizing tax payments and being part of an integrated organization and assessing the performance of each division. This is because multinational companies operate and have subsidiaries in many countries and there is one head office that coordinates global management. The third, as an evaluation of the performance of subsidiaries, maximizes profit receipts by minimizing tax payments and being part of an integrated organization and assessing the performance of each division. This is because multinational companies operate and have subsidiaries in many countries and there is one head office that coordinates global management. The third, as an evaluation of the performance of subsidiaries, maximizes profit receipts by minimizing tax payments and being part of an integrated organization and assessing the performance of each division.

Tax Avoidance

Tax avoidance refers to the activities of company management to reduce or minimize the tax burden owed without violating tax regulations, this aims to maximize company profits. According to Astuti&Aryani (2016) tax avoidance is the behavior of taxpayers in seeking benefits in tax regulations so as to obtain relief in tax payments. Tax avoidance can be said to be a legal practice if it is carried out in accordance with and does not deviate from the established tax rules. Basically tax avoidance is a strategy of tax planning by exploiting gaps, weaknesses or so-called gray areas. As a result, state revenues from the tax sector will decrease, on the other hand the company tries to save on tax payments. For companies, tax is an element of profit margin that affects the rate of return on investment (Siregar&Widyawati, 2016). HoweverThe way a company does to avoid its tax obligations, tax avoidance is an act that can erode a country's revenue from the tax sector.

Hypothesis Development

Transfer pricing is a price determination made by company management to reduce the tax burden, thereby affecting a country's tax revenues and dividends received by shareholders (Herianti&Chairina, 2019). In terms of the practice of avoiding tax flows, the management of the company is engineering the prices contained in transactions between group members to minimize the tax burden or between affiliated companies. Furthermore, determining the price in transfer pricing illogically or exceeding the fair price will lead to tax avoidance practices. In a previous study, according to Maulana et al (2018), they argue that transfer pricing has a positive effect on tax avoidance.

H1: Transfer pricing has an effect on tax avoidance.

Thin capitalization is a company financing mechanism by relying on financing through debt rather than capital (Falbo&Firmansyah, 2018). Excess financing through debt can cause problems in taxation because of the inequality of returns generated from funding in the form of debt and in the form of capital. Funding in the form of capital, which relates to returns in the form of dividends, will be taxed, while debt financing will result in an interest expense which is an element of deducting taxable income. Due to the different characteristics of the treatment between interest and dividends, companies prefer to use debt financing rather than capital. The higher the use of debt, it will increase the practice of tax avoidance (Afifah&Prastiwi, 2019). In previous research, according to Falbo&

H2 : *Thin capitalization* effect on tax avoidance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Data Types and Sources

The author chose secondary data as a source of data in this study. The data collected by the author is adjusted to the above criteria obtained from the annual reports and financial statements of consumer cyclicals sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the 2017-2019 period. Data can be obtained through the IDX portal (www.idx.co.id) and the company's official website.

Population and Sample

The scope of the population that will be used as a population is the consumer cyclicals sector companies that are listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the period 2017, 2018, and 2019. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling (judgment sampling), namely sampling in accordance with the following criteria: criteria.

Operational Definition and Measurement of Variables

***Transfer Pricing*(Independent Variable)**

Measurement of transfer pricing is proxied by observations made by Richardson et al. (2013) in Falbo&Firmansyah (2018). The statistical measure is measured by the sum-score approach, which is the sum of seven indicators taken from the company's financial statements and annual reports and then divided by seven. Here are seven indicators to calculate transfer pricing aggressiveness:

1. There are debts or receivables without interest to related parties.

2. There is an exemption from debts or receivables from or to related parties.
3. There is an impairment in the value of payables or receivables or allowance for bad debts from or to related parties.
4. There are non-monetary obligations in the form of services or taking advantage of non-current assets/leases between related parties.
5. There are no formal documents to support the use of the method *transfer pricing* used in transactions between related parties.
6. There is a disposal of long-term assets from or to related parties without commercial justification.
7. There is no justification that shows that there are transactions between related parties that are carried out fairly.

Thin Capitalization (Independent Variable)

Thin capitalization is a tool to facilitate Prastiwi&Ratnasari's tax avoidance practices (2019). According to Falbo&Firmansyah (2018) there are two stages in measuring thin capitalization as follows:

$$SHDA = (Average\ total\ aset - nonIBL) \times 80\%$$

Mathematically measuring SHDA is the average total assets minus non-IBL (company debt that has nothing to do with interest such as taxes payable, trade payables, customer advances, accounts payable, and so on) (Sulaiman et al., 2019). Then the result is multiplied by 80%. The 80% multiplier is obtained from the thin capitalization rule in Indonesia referring to PMK number 169/PMK.010/2015, because this rule regulates the composition of debt and capital size, which is at most 4:1.

$$MAD\ ratio = \frac{rata-rata\ hutang}{SHDA}$$

The calculation of the MAD ratio in this study is to divide the average debt by SHDA. The calculated value of the MAD ratio is 1 or less than 1 and then converted to a dummy measurement scale. The scale that will be used is if the MAD value is more than 1, it gets a value of 1 and the MAD value is less than 1, it gets a value of 0 (Suntari&Mulyani, 2020).

Tax Avoidance (Dependent Variable)

Tax Avoidance is the practice of minimizing the amount of tax that must be paid by the company by taking advantage of loopholes in a country's laws and regulations (loopholes) and is still justified because it is a legal action. The measurement of the dependent variable of tax avoidance uses the Cash Effective Tax Rate (CETR) measurement which is based on research (Alfarizi et al., 2021).

$$Cash\ ETR = \frac{\sum\ Cash\ Tax\ Paid}{\sum\ Pretax\ Income} \times 100\%$$

Information :

Cash ETR = Effective Tax Rates as a measurement of tax avoidance

Cash Tax Paid= Total tax liability paid by the company (Consolidated statement of cash flows)

Pretax Income= Company's net profit before tax (Consolidated Statement of Comprehensive Income)

Method of collecting data

The data collection method in this study is to collect secondary data by downloading the annual report of the consumer cyclical sector companies listed on the IDX through the portal. www.idx.co.id and the company's official website.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULT

Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

Table 8. Simultaneous Significance Test (Test F)

ANOVAa						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	,183	2	,091	4,153	0.019b
	Residual	1,980	90	,022		
	Total	2,163	92			

- a. Dependent Variable: Lag_Y1
 - b. Predictors: (Constant), Lag_X2, Lag_X1
- Source: SPSS v26 Processing Results

The test results in table 8 show the value of sig. ie $0.000 < 0.05$. So that the two independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on tax avoidance.

Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)
Table 9. Coefficient of Determination Test (R2)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,291a	,084	,064	,14834

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Lag_X2, Lag_X1
- Source: SPSS v26 Processing Results

Based on table 9 the value of the coefficient of determination shows the results of Adjusted R Square (R2) 0.064, which means that the effect of transfer pricing (X1) and thin capitalization (X2) variables simultaneously on the dependent variable, namely tax avoidance is 6.4%. The remaining 93.6% (100-6.4) can be explained by other variables.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 10. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	,196	,061		3.232	,002
Lag_X1	,139	,198	,071	,704	,483
Lag_X2	,139	0.051	,276	2,726	,008

- a. Dependent Variable: Lag_Y1
- Source: SPSS v26 Processing Results

V. DISCUSSION

Effect of transfer pricing on tax avoidance

It can be seen from the test results in table 10 partially (t test) that the transfer pricing variable in this observation does not have a significant effect on tax avoidance. This can be explained by the acquisition of a significance value of 0.483 > which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Based on these results, it can be concluded empirically that transfer pricing has no effect on tax avoidance. So in the absence of the effect of transfer pricing on tax avoidance, it is thus explained that the first hypothesis is rejected.

Effect of thin capitalization on tax avoidance

It can be seen from the test results in table 10 partially (t test) that the thin capitalization variable in this observation has a significant effect on tax avoidance. This can be explained by the acquisition of a significance value of 0.008 < 0.05 which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. Based on these results, it can be concluded that empirically thin capitalization has an influence on tax avoidance. So with the effect of thin capitalization on tax avoidance, so that it is explained if the second hypothesis is accepted.

VI. CONCLUSION

Research Conclusion

Based on observations that have been carried out through various stages such as collecting data, processing data, analyzing data and finally interpreting the results of the analysis regarding the effect of transfer pricing and thin capitalization on tax avoidance by using data that normally distributed, free from multicollinearity, free from autocorrelation and there is no heteroscedasticity problem, then the information can be generated as follows:

1. From the results of data analysis, it is found that the transfer pricing variable has no effect on tax avoidance. This result can be seen through the significance level of transfer pricing which is 0.483 which exceeds the regulatory limit of <0.05 . So the first hypothesis which reveals transfer pricing has an effect on tax avoidance is rejected.
2. From the results of data analysis, it is obtained that the thin capitalization variable has an influence on tax avoidance. This result can be seen through the significance level of transfer pricing which gets a figure of 0.008 which is less than the regulatory limit, which is <0.05 . So the first hypothesis which reveals that thin capitalization affects tax avoidance is accepted. Limitations

From the observations that have been carried out, it is found that in this observation the consumer cyclicals sector companies in the period 2017 to 2019 that were chosen to be the sample of this study experienced many losses, this will have an impact on the negative CETR value. This will result in diminishing data because the criteria that have been written only include the CETR 0-1 value of each company. The consideration is that when the company suffers a loss, the company is exempted by the state in paying tax obligations, while when the company makes a profit, it is impossible for the company to get tax free or not get tax payment obligations. This has an impact on the results of conclusions that are less broad and comprehensive.

In addition, this study provides information that the adjusted r square (R^2) is only 0.053 or 6.4% of the dependent variable, namely tax avoidance, which can be explained by the two independent variables, namely transfer pricing and thin capitalization. The remaining 93.6% can be explained by other variables. This shows that the data can be categorized as poor because the independent variable is less able to explain the dependent variable. Due to the greater the value of adjusted r square in the study, the better the resulting data will be.

Suggestion

It is hoped that further research can select samples from companies in other sectors in the hope of being able to provide representative observation results and it is advisable to choose a research period with a longer period so that the results obtained are more representative and can be generalized and use tax avoidance measurements other than cash effective tax rate (CETR), such as total Book Tax Different (BTD) and so on.

In future research, it is expected to determine other variables that have a major contribution in influencing tax avoidance that occurs in the company, this is intended so that the results obtained have value.

adjusted r square even higher so that tax avoidance can be better explained by the selected independent variables. Where in this observation has a weakness, namely the dependent variable can only be explained by the independent variable of 6.4%.

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